

Complex Polymetaphosphates of Strongly Electropositive Elements

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SYNTHESIS and characterisation of high molecular weight chain phosphates, e.g., Graham's salt $(\text{NaPO}_3)_n$ and related derivatives, have received considerable attention in recent years with the growing interest in the field of inorganic polymers and polyelectrolytes. Various aspects of their chemistry have been extensively reviewed¹⁻⁹. Since the observations of Hall¹⁰ in 1934, Graham's salt (called calgon, i.e., calcium gone) has been extensively employed in sequestration of metal ions with special application in water softening.

Earlier studies¹¹⁻¹⁸ regarding the complexation of calcium, magnesium and other cations by Graham's salt in solution showed the formation of complexes with the formulae, $\text{Na}_2\text{M}_2\text{P}_6\text{O}_{18}$; these formulae were based on the then accepted hexameric nature of Graham's salt. Mehrotra¹⁷ showed the versatility of the complexation tendencies of Graham's salt with a large number of cations, e.g., alkali, alkaline and rare-earth metals, Be, Al, Zr, Th, Fe, Ni, Cu, Zn, Cd, Hg, Pb etc. Dhar and Mehrotra¹⁸ synthesized a number of complexes of Graham's salt with calcium, strontium, barium, zinc, magnesium and lead in the form of glassy solids and assigned to them a formulation of the type $[\text{Na}_x\text{M}_{1-x/2}(\text{PO}_3)_6]_n$. Long chain polymeric character of Graham's salt was established with the help of several physicochemical techniques, viz. ultracentrifugation¹⁹, dialysis²⁰, end-group titrations²¹, viscosity measurements^{22,23}, light scattering²⁴, conductometry²⁵, electrolytic transference studies²⁶, chromatography^{27,28}, fractional precipitation²⁹, X-ray diffraction³⁰ etc. The above derivatives can therefore be interpreted to contain anions of the type $[\text{Na}_x\text{M}(\text{PO}_3)_6]_n^{2n-}$. This conclusion is supported by the findings of Wall and Doremus³¹ based on their electrolytic transference studies also.

Later on, a large number of complex polymetaphosphate derivatives of Graham's salt of the composition $[\text{Na}_x\text{M}_{1-x/a}(\text{PO}_3)_6]_n$ [where $\text{M}=\text{K}, \text{Li}, \text{Ca}, \text{Ba}, \text{Zn}, \text{Cu}$ or Fe(III) ; $x=2/3, 1/2$ or $1/3$ and a is valency of metal M] were synthesised in the glassy form by Gupta³². These derivatives were found to be polymeric in nature similar to that of Graham's salt and exhibited polyelectrolytic behaviour³³⁻⁴⁰.

The polymetaphosphate of more electropositive metal potassium $(\text{KPO}_3)_n$, known as potassium Kurrol's salt, has been synthesised by thermal dehydration of KH_2PO_4 ⁴¹. It differs from Graham's salt in being insoluble in water and

having a different structure in the solid state⁴². Andress and Fischer⁴³ showed by X-ray studies that the anions of the compound consist of polymeric chains of $(\text{PO}_3)_n^{n-}$ units. Following the X-ray diffraction studies of Corbridge⁴⁴, Jost⁴⁵ has shown that crystals of $(\text{KPO}_3)_n$ are monoclinic belonging to the space group, $\text{P}_{21/a}$ with lattice constants as $a=14.02\text{\AA}$, $b=4.54\text{\AA}$, $c=10.28\text{\AA}$ and $\alpha=111.5^\circ$. The polyphosphate chain is of screw type and contains four PO_4 tetrahedra per period so that each potassium is surrounded by seven or eight oxygen atoms. According to Jost, the swelling in water or salt solutions and ion-exchange behaviour of $(\text{KPO}_3)_n$ can be attributed to relatively weak forces between 201 planes.

Keeping in view the solubility characteristics^{46,47} and ion-exchange behaviour⁴⁸ of $(\text{KPO}_3)_n$, it was predicted by Mehrotra *et al*⁴⁹ that complex derivatives of the type $[\text{K}_x\text{M}_{1-x/a}(\text{PO}_3)_6]_n$ should behave differently and should probably be soluble in water. This conjecture has been confirmed by the synthesis of complex potassium polymetaphosphate glasses of mono and divalent metal ions. The complex derivatives of the composition $[\text{K}_x\text{M}_{1-x/a}(\text{PO}_3)_6]_n$ (where $\text{M}=\text{Li}, \text{Na}, \text{Ca}, \text{Sr}, \text{Ba}, \text{Zn}, \text{Cd}, \text{Cu}, \text{Ni}$ or Pb ; $x=2/3, 1/2$ or $1/3$ and a is valency of metal M) were synthesised, employing a fusion reaction (at 800°) of MO ($\text{M}=\text{bivalent metal}$), $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{HPO}_4$ with KH_2PO_4 . A few of the reactions have been followed by thermogravimetric and differential thermal analysis to throw light on the mechanism of the condensation reactions and the nature of the product formed. All these complex derivatives were obtained as clear, transparent glasses. The complex derivatives with $x=2/3$ were found to be easily soluble in water, but the solubility decreased with increasing ratio of the bivalent metal ion to potassium. The nature of these derivatives has been found to be similar to that of Graham's salt and other related compounds⁵⁰⁻⁵².

In view of the observed water soluble nature of these derivatives, it can be assumed that during dissolution of $(\text{KPO}_3)_n$ in salt solutions of electrolytes or in the suspension of cation exchange resin, formation of complex polymetaphosphate derivatives of the type synthesised by fusion technique takes place. This assumption has been verified in a different manner as well. When an aqueous suspension of potassium Kurrol's salt and a bivalent metal polymetaphosphate $[\text{M}(\text{PO}_3)_6]_n$ in a molar ratio 4 : 1 is shaken together for a long time,

mutual dissolution of these two virtually insoluble derivatives takes place. On adding alcohol to the clear solutions thus obtained, precipitation of complex potassium polymetaphosphate derivatives of the composition $[K_x M(PO_3)_n \cdot 2H_2O]_n$ ($M=Ca, Sr, Ba, Pb$ or Cd) takes place⁵³. These reactions are thus corroborative of the parallelism envisaged by Thilo⁴⁸, between complexation reactions of polyphosphates and ion-exchange behaviour of synthetic ion-exchange resins.

Lithium polymetaphosphate ($LiPO_3$)_n has a structure similar to diopside and thus differs from $(KPO_3)_n$ and $(CsPO_3)_n$. It is also obtained as a glassy product during thermal dehydration of lithium dihydrogen orthophosphate and is soluble in water like Graham's salt and cesium polymetaphosphate. The size of Li^+ cation is smaller than that of other alkali metal cations and it is also smaller than those of more electropositive bivalent metal ions. Therefore, its exchange by other cations in $(LiPO_3)_n$ should be comparatively lesser. The binding of alkali metal ions with polyphosphate chain has been investigated by Strauss *et al*⁵⁴. The specific site bonding of cations on $(PO_3)_n^{n-}$ chain follows the order $Li^+ > Na^+ > K^+ > Cs^+ > Ca^{2+} > (CH_3)_4N^+$. Thus, it was expected that the complex derivatives of lithium polymetaphosphate should behave in a different manner. Hence, complex lithium polymetaphosphate derivatives of the composition $[Li_x M_{1-x/n} PO_3]_n$ (where $M = Ca, Sr, Ba, Mg, Be, Cu, Ni, Cd, Zn, Pb$ etc.; $x=2/3, 1/2$ and $1/3$ and n is valency of metal M) were synthesized by Mehrotra and Oza⁵⁵. All these derivatives were obtained as hygroscopic glassy solids. These were found to be water soluble, polymeric in nature and exhibited characteristic properties similar to that of Graham's salt and its complex derivatives⁵⁶⁻⁵⁸.

Cesium shows a close resemblance to potassium in its chemical properties. Cesium polymetaphosphate, $(CsPO_3)_n$, although isomorphous with potassium polymetaphosphate, is soluble in water unlike the latter. The course of thermal dehydration of KH_2PO_4 and CsH_2PO_4 has been studied with the help of complementary TGA, DTA and X-ray studies^{59,60}. In both the systems $[MH_2PO_4 \cdot (MPO_3)_n]$ formation of trimetaphosphate is precluded and lower chain phosphates are directly converted to polymetaphosphates. In $NaH_2PO_4 \cdot (NaPO_3)_n$ system, a large number of condensed phosphate anions exists as intermediate products varying in nature with temperature and duration of heating. The water vapour pressure also plays an important role in stabilizing a particular product. Keeping this in view, cesium polymetaphosphate and its complex derivatives were synthesised⁵⁵ by fusion techniques. These derivatives of the composition $[Cs_x M_{1-x/n} PO_3]_n$ (where $x=1, 2/3, 1/2$ or $1/3$; $M=K, Ca, Sr, Zn, Cd$ or Pb and n is valency of metal M) are glassy solids except $(CsPO_3)_n$ which is obtained as an opaque mass. The investigations⁶¹⁻⁶³ of physicochemical properties of these derivatives have revealed a close similarity with Graham's salt and other complex alkali polymetaphosphates.

Among the polymetaphosphates of trivalent metal ions, synthesis of $[Fe(PO_3)_3]_n$ has been reported by Dyvoire⁶⁴ who obtained it by heating $Fe(H_2PO_4)_3$ to a temperature greater than 850° . The reaction of $FeCl_3$ with $(NaPO_3)_n$ in solution was investigated by Mehrotra and Gupta⁶⁰. It was established with the help of pH-metric and conductometric studies that compounds of the composition $[Fe_2(OH)_2(PO_3)_6]_n$ is formed instead of the expected $[Fe(PO_3)_3]_n$ derivative. The simple Fe(III) polymetaphosphate or complex sodium-iron polymetaphosphate could not be synthesized by fusion technique. Lanthanum and other lanthanide elements have electronegativity values in the range of alkaline earth metals. Their characteristic oxidation state is +3. It is worthwhile to mention here that polymetaphosphates of trivalent lanthanides can not be prepared by thermal dehydration of their acid orthophosphates. The complexation reactions of lanthanides with some oligophosphates have been investigated by some Russian workers⁶⁴⁻⁶⁶. However, their long chain polyphosphates have not been synthesised. Hence, the reactions of lanthanum, yttrium and cerium(III) nitrates with alkali metal polymetaphosphates have been investigated by pH-metric and conductometric technique. On the basis of results obtained from these studies polymetaphosphate derivatives of the composition $[M(PO_3)_3]_n$ could be obtained as precipitates. A soluble complex derivative of the composition $[Na_{1/2} La_{1/6} (PO_3)_n]_n$ could also be obtained by precipitation technique for the first time, and its polymeric as well as polyelectrolytic characteristics have been investigated.

Experimental

(A) Synthesis :

(i) *Preparation of complex polymetaphosphates of potassium with lithium or cesium* : The above complex glasses were synthesized at 800° by the fusion reactions of the following type :

(where $M=Li$ or Cs ; $x=2/3, 1/2$ or $1/3$)

(ii) *Synthesis of polymetaphosphates of yttrium lanthanum and cerium* : When solutions of lithium, sodium or cesium polymetaphosphates, $(MPO_3)_n$, synthesised as described earlier^{52,49,55}, were mixed with metal salt solutions in the molar ratio 3 : 1 precipitates were obtained. The reactions could be expressed as follows :

(iii) *Synthesis of the complex derivative $[Na_{1/2} La_{1/6} PO_3]_n$* : This complex derivative was separated by the addition of alcohol to a clear solution obtained by mixing sodium polymetaphosphate solution and lanthanum nitrate solution in the molar ratio 6 : 1.

The precipitate thus obtained was dried at reduced pressure at room temperature.

All the above derivatives (I-III) synthesized during the present investigations were analysed for metal and phosphorus contents (Table 1).

III. Paper chromatographic studies were carried out on a Whatman No. 1 chromatographic filter paper employing Ebel's⁴⁹ acidic solvent. R_f and R_g values for different polymer samples were recorded (Table 2).

IV. pH-metric titrations of yttrium, lanthanum and cerium(III) salt solutions with alkali polymetaphosphate (MPO_3)_n solutions were performed employing a 'Cambridge' bench type pH-meter and

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS OF SIMPLE AND COMPLEX POLYMETAPHOSPHATE DERIVATIVES

Formula of the compd. and mode of synthesis Synthesized by fusion at 800°	% metal M'		% metal M''		% Phos.	
	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
[K _{2/3} Li _{1/3} PO ₃] _n	23.71	24.27	2.11	2.15	28.71	28.84
[K _{1/2} Li _{1/2} PO ₃] _n	19.13	19.17	3.38	3.40	30.33	30.38
[K _{1/3} Li _{2/3} PO ₃] _n	13.70	13.76	4.77	4.79	31.99	32.06
[Cs _{2/3} K _{1/3} PO ₃] _n	—	—	7.30	7.22	17.20	17.16
[K _{1/2} Ca _{1/4} PO ₃] _n	17.03	17.08	13.86	13.89	27.03	27.08
Obtained by precipitation from clear solution						
[Na _{1/2} La _{1/6} PO ₃ .H ₂ O] _n	—	—	24.05	23.55	17.88	17.59
Obtained as precipitates						
[La(PO ₃) ₃] _n dried at 135°	27.10	26.98	—	—	24.57	24.73
[Y(PO ₃) ₃ .3H ₂ O] _n dried over pump	23.52	23.41	—	—	24.35	24.46
[Ce(PO ₃) ₃ .3H ₂ O] _n dried over pump	32.37	32.50	—	—	21.29	21.56

(B) Physicochemical properties of the new derivatives :

(I) Number average molecular weights of all these derivatives were determined by end-group titration technique^{29,67}. As suggested by Gustavsson and Larsson⁶⁸, a dilute hydrochloric acid solution was added to bring the pH of the polymer solution upto 3.0 to 3.5. On titration with sodium hydroxide solution, two breaks were obtained at pH values around 4 and 9 and from this titre value, the number average molecular weights (Mn) of the polymer can be calculated by the formula.

$$Mn = \frac{2000 \times \text{wt of polymer dissolved in solution}}{\text{ml of } N \text{ NaOH required}}$$

The Mn values are recorded in Table 2.

TABLE 2— R_f AND R_g VALUES FOR COMPLEX ALKALI POLYMETAPHOSPHATE DERIVATIVES IN EBEL'S ACIDIC SOLVENT (FLOW TIME -20 hr) ALONG WITH THEIR NUMBER AVERAGE MOLECULAR WEIGHTS (Mn)

Formula of the compound	R_f	R_g	Mn
[K _{2/3} Li _{1/3} PO ₃] _n	0.10	0.14	4000
[K _{1/2} Li _{1/2} PO ₃] _n	0.09	0.12	5000
[K _{1/3} Li _{2/3} PO ₃] _n	0.10	0.14	4500
[K _{1/2} Ca _{1/4} PO ₃] _n	0.14	0.20	3300
[Cs _{2/3} K _{1/3} PO ₃] _n	0.030	0.042	12000
[Na _{1/2} La _{1/6} PO ₃] _n	0.08	0.12	7000
(NaPO ₃) _n	0.064	0.084	8000
(LiPO ₃) _n	0.068	0.090	6000
(CsPO ₃) _n	0.027	0.039	12000

II. Conductance measurements at different formal concentration of the polymer solution were carried out on a RLC Tesla bridge employing a Philips Conductivity Cell (cell factor 1.49). The plots of equivalent conductance versus square root of concentrations are shown in Fig. 1.

glass and calomel electrodes. Fig. 2 shows the pH-titrations of La(NO₃)₃ with alkali polymetaphosphate solutions.

Conductometric titrations of yttrium, lanthanum and cerium(III) salt solutions were also performed on RLC Tesla bridge, employing a 'Philips' conductivity cell. Fig. 3 shows the plot of specific conductance versus moles of alkalipolymetaphosphate added during the titration of lanthanum nitrate with alkalipolyphosphates.

Results and Discussion

General: Unlike potassium Kurrol's salt (KPO₃)_n, the complex polymetaphosphate derivatives [K_xLi_{1-x}PO₃]_n (where x=2/3, 1/2 or 1/3) were obtained as clear transparent glasses and were found to be soluble in water. This is expected keeping in view the ion-exchange behaviour of alkali polymetaphosphates⁴⁶. Similar observations have been reported earlier by Mehrotra and Vyas during their studies on complex potassium polymetaphosphate derivatives⁵⁰⁻⁵³. However, in the case of complex cesium polymetaphosphate derivatives containing potassium and cesium it has been found that only one derivative i.e. [Cs_{2/3}K_{1/3}PO₃]_n was found to be soluble in water whereas the other two derivatives i.e. [Cs_{1/2}K_{1/2}PO₃]_n and [Cs_{1/3}K_{2/3}PO₃]_n did not dissolve in water even after prolonged shaking. Thus, with the increase in ratio of potassium in the polyphosphate chain the solubility diminishes. In the case of complex lithium derivatives of potassium Kurrol's salt the solubility of the compounds in all mole ratios could be ascribed to effective ion-exchange of K⁺ by small Li⁺ ions, whereas larger K⁺ ions are not able to do so when the ratio K⁺/Cs⁺ increases. Ohashi and coworkers⁴⁵

Fig. 1. Plot of equivalent conductance versus square root of concentration.

have also observed that in aqueous solutions of bivalent metal ions the exchange of K^+ can occur to the extent of 82-94% in the potassium Kurrol's salt. The insolubility of the complex polymetaphosphate derivatives of barium and strontium of the composition $[K_{1/3}M_{1/3}PO_3]_n$ and $[K_{1/3}M_{1/4}PO_3]_n$ ($M=Ba$ or Sr) suggests that exchange of K^+ ion by Ba^{2+} and Sr^{2+} ions can occur only to the extent of less than 50%. The exchange of K^+ ion by Ca^{2+} in $(KPO_3)_n$ can occur to the extent of 50% as evident from the solubility of the complex derivative $(K_{1/2}Ca_{1/4}PO_3)_n$. The above behaviour seems plausible in view of the formation of dianionic

chains of the type given below, as suggested by Eisenberg⁷⁰.

Fig. 2. 25 ml $M/250$ $\text{La}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ titrated pH-metrically against $M/100[\text{NaPO}_3]_n$, $\square[\text{LiPO}_3]_n$ and $\triangle[\text{CsPO}_3]_n$.

Fig. 3. 25ml $M/250$ $\text{La}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ titrated conductometrically against $M/100[\text{NaPO}_3]_n$, $\square[\text{LiPO}_3]_n$ and $\triangle[\text{CsPO}_3]_n$.

The formation of such cross linked structures might result in increasing the lattice force making the exchange of ions difficult.

Complexation reactions of $(\text{MPO}_3)_n$ with La^{3+} , Ce^{3+} and Y^{3+} : Synthesis of simple or complex polymetaphosphate derivatives of lanthanum and other lanthanides was tried by fusion method but a melt could not be obtained even at a temperature of 1100° . During the pH-metric and conductometric titrations of Y^{3+} , La^{3+} and Ce^{3+} salt solutions with $(\text{MPO}_3)_n$ solutions ($M=\text{Li, Na}$ or Cs) it was found that precipitation occurs till $\text{Ln}^{3+}:\text{P}$ ratio equals $1:3$. At this stage an inflection can be seen in the titration curves (Figs. 2, 3). Hence the compounds $[\text{Ln}(\text{PO}_3)_3]_n$ ($\text{Ln}=\text{Y}^{3+}, \text{La}^{3+}$ or Ce^{3+}) were isolated by mixing $\text{La}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ solutions and $(\text{MPO}_3)_n$ solutions (where $M=\text{Li, Na}$

or Cs) in the molar ratio $1:3$. The precipitates obtained were washed with water, dried and analysed for metal and phosphorus. The analyses (Table 1) corresponds to the above composition.

During the above titration, it can be observed that the precipitate starts dissolving on addition of excess (>3 moles) of $(\text{MPO}_3)_n$ solution. Thus, in the titration of $\text{La}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ with $(\text{NaPO}_3)_n$ a clear solution was obtained at $\text{La}:\text{P}$ ratio of $1:6$. This indicated the formation of a complex derivative of the composition $[\text{Na}_{1/2}\text{La}_{2/6}\text{PO}_3]_n$. It was isolated by mixing together $\text{La}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ solution and $(\text{NaPO}_3)_n$ solution in molar ratio $1:6$ and adding ethanol. The precipitate obtained was washed with alcohol and dried under reduced pressure. It was analysed for lanthanum and phosphorus and the composition was found to be $[\text{Na}_{1/2}\text{La}_{2/6}\text{PO}_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]_n$ (Table 1).

Number average molecular weights (M_n) of complex polymetaphosphate: The number average molecular weight (M_n) data (Table 2) suggest polymeric nature of the complex polymetaphosphate synthesized as above. The M_n values of complex potassium lithium polymetaphosphate were found to be in the range of $4000-5000$ while that of $[\text{Cs}_{2/3}\text{K}_{1/3}\text{PO}_3]_n$ was found to be 12000 . It has been reported that most of the polymetaphosphate derivatives of lithium have molecular weights in the range $3500-5000$. Cesium polymetaphosphate and its complex derivatives have molecular weights (M_n) in the range $10000-12000$. These data suggest that in presence of small strongly binding counter ions, a greater degree of cross linking through the formation of dianionic chain results and hence these derivatives are characterized by low M_n values. Eisenberg⁷⁰ in a study of the polyphosphate polymers, homopolymers containing Li^+ , Na^+ , Ca^{2+} , Ba^{2+} , Zn^{2+} and counter ion polymeric systems such as $\text{Na}^+\text{-La}^{3+}$, $\text{Na}^+\text{-Ca}^{2+}$, $\text{Na}^+\text{-K}^+$, $\text{K}^+\text{-Li}^+$ in the glass transition range revealed that the diionic chains possess cross linking character as compared to those in which the repeat units contain only one type of cation. The molecular weights of $[\text{Na}_{1/2}\text{La}_{2/6}\text{PO}_3]_n$ sample obtained by precipitation technique was found to be in the range of 7000 , whereas the molecular weight of the Graham's salt sample from which it was synthesized was around 10000 . It, however, indicates that the compound possesses polymeric nature similar to that of Graham's salt.

Polyelectrolytic character: The conductance of complex polymetaphosphate solutions are generally in the same range (within $15-20\%$) as that of the simple alkalipolymetaphosphates from which these derivatives are obtained. The equivalent conductance at different formal concentrations are given in Table 2. This indicates that the mobilities of the anions are not markedly affected by the complete or partial substitution of alkali metal by other metal ions. This is in conformity with the structures suggested by Mehrotra¹⁷. Wall and Doremus⁸¹ also shown in 1954 that the ionic mobilities of polyanions in the solutions of $(\text{NaPO}_3)_n$ and

$(\text{Na}_{1/2}\text{Sr}_{1/4}\text{PO}_3)_n$ are of the same order. The plot of equivalent conductance λ , versus square root of concentration $\sqrt{C}$, (Fig. 1) is typical of polyelectrolytes i.e., has parabolic shape. Thus, the conductance measurements demonstrate the polyelectrolytic nature of these complex derivatives.

Paper chromatographic studies : The paper chromatographic studies of the complex polymetaphosphate derivatives were carried out in acidic solvents. The R_f and R_o values are recorded in Table 2. From these values it can be seen that the R_f and R_o values for the complex compounds are in close agreement with those for Graham's salt and other alkali polyphosphates and are different from those reported for trimetaphosphates and other lower phosphates. This indicates a long chain polymeric character for these derivatives just similar to that of Graham's salt. A very weak spot due to the trimetaphosphates is also observed which is probably due to the hydrolysis of the polymetaphosphates during the course of the flow of the solvent. Trailing effect was observed in some cases but the R_f and R_o values could be calculated without much difficulty.

Hence, it is clear from these studies that the complex polymetaphosphate derivatives containing more than one electro positive metals have almost all the characteristics similar to that observed for Graham's salt and other related compounds. It can thus be concluded that all these derivatives, although containing different metal combinations and synthesized in different manners, have properties similar to that for Graham's salt and other long chain polyphosphates.

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